

RISC-V is on a roll, and there are plenty of projects using the open-source instruction set architecture funded by the European Union, as reported in *HiPEACinfo 66*. One of the latest is RISER, which will develop the first all-European RISC-V cloud server infrastructure, significantly enhancing Europe's strategic autonomy in open-source technologies.

RISER: Raising RISC-V to the cloud

RISER will leverage and validate open hardware high-speed interfaces combined with a fully featured operating system environment and runtime system, enabling the integration of low-power components, including RISC-V processor chips from the European Processor Initiative (EPI) and EUPILLOT projects, in a novel energy-efficient cloud architecture.

RISER brings together seven partners from industry and academia to jointly develop and validate open-source designs for standardized form-factor system platforms, suitable for supporting cloud services. Specifically, RISER will build two cloud-focused platforms:

- (1) An accelerator PCIe card integrating up to four RISC-V chips derived from the EUPILLOT project eupilot.eu. This accelerator can plug-in into any PCIe-enabled system on chip (SoC), whether ARM or x86.
- (2) A cloud services platform, interconnecting microserver boards developed by the project, each one supporting up to four RISC-V chips coupled with high-speed storage and networking. Embracing hyperconvergence, the RISER microserver architecture allows for distributed storage and memory to be used by any processor in the system with low overhead. The open-source system board designs of RISER will be accompanied by open-source low-level firmware and systems software, and a representative Linux-based software stack to support cloud services, facilitating uptake and enhancing the commercialization path of project results.

Three use cases will be developed to evaluate and demonstrate the capabilities of RISER platforms:

- a) Acceleration of compute workloads;
- b) Networked object and key-value storage;
- c) Containerized execution as part of a provider-managed IaaS environment.

PROJECT NAME: RISER: RISC-V for cloud services

START/END DATE: 01/01/2023 - 31/12/2025

KEY THEMES: RISC-V, open hardware interfaces, PCIe accelerator board, microserver, boot firmware, Linux operating system, open-source software stack for cloud services

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BUDGET: €5,316,125

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FURTHER INFORMATION:

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